

Decline in the Handloom Cottage Industry: A Case Study of Handloom Bunkars of Varanasi

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Abstract

When we automate then we modernise it and when we automate human life then we primitivise it (Eric Hoffer, 1951). Banarasi saree is not just a cloth it is an alive proof of India's handloom. Banarasi sarees are beautifully designed by the use of gold and silver zari and also recognised as the queen of all the sarees. It is evident from the available fact that even during the Vedic period there was wide use of sarees for different purposes. These handloom products reach to its peak with the coming of Mughals in India. Due to the long history of colonization handloom products lost its glory during the British regime. With the main objective of analysing and identifying the factors responsible for the continuous decline in the living condition of handloom bunkars, the study has been undertaken. Based on the global experience, observation, analysis about the handloom bunkars and local perceptions about them a household survey was conducted in December 2016 in Bazarhdeeha handloom cluster of Varanasi, Uttar Pradesh. Primary data has been tabulated and appropriate statistical method has been used. Arc GIS 10.3 version software has been used to digitize Varanasi map. It was noted that certain government schemes have an adverse impact on the livelihood of bunkars. Though the Geographical Indication tag has been given to Banarasi saree in 2009 but, it didn't provide any kind of relief to the handloom bunkars of Varanasi. It was also suggested that the strong political will help in the revival of handloom cottage industry of Varanasi. Apart from this linking of handloom cottage industry with the online will result in the comprehensive growth of this sector.

Keywords: Sustained, Colonization, Morphology, Geographical Indication and Comprehensive.

Introduction

Handloom cottage industry provides second largest number of employment in India just after the agriculture because like the agriculture it is also a labour intensive sector. It plays a vital role in the growth of Indian economy (Sana, 2016). Handloom cottage industry more or less sustained itself from the Vedic times by the process of passing their rich cultural heritage from one generation to the next generation (Tarun, 2015). Banarasi sarees are prepared with the Jacquard handlooms and are not only famous in India but also in different parts of the world. Banarasi sarees are made up of very fine embroidery work and that fine embroidery is the uniqueness of it (Shaleni et al., 2015). Banarasi sarees have emblematic fabrics and in that fabrics, several patterns are

also developed by the use of gold and silver zari (Savitri et al., 2013). These zari are woven at a different interval to get the desired design. Here, the yarn of zari also knitted to prepare several design in Banarasi saree (Table 1). Banaras in present times also called as Varanasi.

Weaving (Fig. 1) industry of Varanasi is cluster-based and there are several handloom clusters in Varanasi like Saraiyan, Bazarhdeeha, Jalalipura, Baragaon etc. Banarasi sarees also adopt different changes in its design, orientation, fabrics and products (Dr. Jasminder, 2016). In handloom sector, both male and female member of the bunkar family is engaged in the process of saree preparation (Jyoti and Suman, 2016). But, the work of female members are confined within the four s.

walls of the bunkars house like wrapping (Fig. 2) and unwrapping of thread while male members handle the core weaving of saree and outside work like drying and colouring (Fig. 3). With the adoption of Liberalisation, Privatisation and Globalisation (LPG policy) where the main focus was on the manufacturing sector and not on the handloom cottage. In the early 1990s, war among Gulf countries like Iran, Iraq, Kuwait and Saudi Arabia. Introduction of synthetic, duplicate and cheap silk. Very tough competition with the Chinese sarees in the domestic and international markets. Abolition of child labour laws and so on. All these factors put the future of rich cultural heritage of handloom cottage industry in that age from where it becomes very difficult to revive its glory again (Yasin, 2016).

Review Background

In the Vedic period, Varanasi was also called by the name Kashi which was famous as Shiv Ki Nagri. Prosperity of handloom cottage industry can be seen from our Vedic literature (Handloom Annual Report, 2014-15). During that time, sarees made up of gold and silver

thread were also worn by the rich and upper class of the kingdom like queen, princess etc. These sarees depicts their rich tradition, culture and custom. In the medieval times, skilled Muslim weavers from the West Asia came to India along with the Mughals (Shoab, 2016). In Varanasi, Hindu bunkars already have excellence in the motifs of handloom weaving and the fusion of Muslim bunkars with them results in the excellent weaving of sarees like Banarasi silk meena (Fig. 4), Banarasi organza etc. and its different products like pillow cover (Fig. 5) cushion cover and so on (Amrita and Shailaja, 2009).

It is very peculiar to notice that Muslim bunkars in their handloom products never use figure of any living things like animals, birds, fishes, story-telling of different mythology such as Mahabharat, Ramayan, Jatak stories etc. Because in Islam, it is totally restricted to draw the figure of any living objects while Hindu bunkars are very frequently using these things. Though, with the coming of Muslims designs in the shape of vegetation and flowers were added to the India's handloom sarees (Raj, 2016).

Table 1: Three Categories of Banarasi Fabrics

Brocades Types	Characteristics
Zari Fabric	Type of fabric entirely made up of zari (gold and silver) depend on the demand of the consumer.
Amru Fabric	Entirely golden silk is used which gives gorgeous look to the Banarasi saree.
Muslin Fabric	Mainly used on the bottom of Banarasi sarees the golden zari.

Source: Primary Survey (Author, 2016)

The Study Area

Varanasi is called as the city of light (Eck, 1982). Holy sites made up of physical and man-made combination of the sacred symbols and morphology and these two have sacred meaning. For example, in Varanasi, there are different sacred ghats like Manikarnika ghat, Valmiki ghat, Dashashwamedh ghat (Tanaka,

1998). Varanasi is older than culture, older than history, older than tradition, even twice older than all of us kept together (Niels Gutschow, 1994). Varanasi is located in the northern part of Uttar Pradesh between 25° 14' to 25° 23' north and 82° 55' to 83° 04' east co-ordinates (Fig. 7). Varanasi is called as cultural and ancient city of India. Varanasi lies on the higher

levees of river Ganga which is about six meters long. It has a secure and safe location from its all three sides i.e. Varuna river lies to its north, Assi ghat lies to its south and in the east, it is

surrounded by Ganga river. Tropical monsoon climate can be seen in Varanasi with the good amount of rainfall (The Gazette of India, 2009).

Fig. 1: Weaving (Author, 2016)

Fig. 2: Wrapping (Author, 2016)

Fig. 3: Colouring (Author, 2016)

Fig. 4: Banaras Silk Meena (Author, 2016)

Fig. 5: Pillow Cover (Author, 2016)

Fig. 6: Raw Material Shop (Author, 2016)

Fig. 7

It lies 85 meters above the mean sea level. Varanasi shares its boundary with Jaunpur to its west, Ghazipur to its north, Chandauli to its east and Mirzapur to its south. The total population of Varanasi is 3.67 million which is spread over an area of 1525 sq. km. (Census of India, 2011). Handloom bunkars of Varanasi have been selected because I am observing them from a very long time and have a keen interest in this topic. Know the insights condition of the bunkars and the ground reality about the socio-economic aspect of Varanasi bunkars. Which kind of financial and logistic support, they need from the different stakeholders? Like co-operatives, samities, corporation, ministry etc. who are all involved in the growth and development of handloom bunkars of Varanasi.

Objective

Analysing the reasons behind the decline in the living condition of Varanasi handloom bunkars.

Database and Methodology

Primary Survey Regarding this, purposely random survey was conducted in Varanasi district of Uttar Pradesh in December 2016. It composes of 50 participants from the different age-group with the range 20-70 years in order to understand the comprehensive picture of the decline in the handloom cottage industry of Varanasi. In this regard, out of nine clusters, Bazarhdeeha has been selected. For that respondents were divided into 5 categories like 20-30 years, 30-40 years 40-50 years, 50-60 years and 60-70 years. Ten respondents were selected from each division irrespective of male and female. Regarding this, a questionnaire comprises of both open and close ended questions has been prepared. The main focus of the question is regarding the people thoughts, ideas and perception for the decline of rich handloom cultural heritage of Varanasi. What are the steps till now have been taken for its revival? What are their future expectation from the government to revive it? In order to understand the mindset of the respondent and to get familiar with this study area of

Bazarhdeeha, a pilot survey of this study area in late November 2016. After ten days of pilot survey, full survey of Bazarhdeeha has been conducted. Varanasi district map has been digitized with all its handloom clusters by the help of Arc GIS 10.3 version. During the digitization of Varanasi district map, many problems like setting of coordinates, labelling of latitude and longitudes have been faced. All these problems were sorted out by taking the help of experts. During the interview process, very few female respondent have been found because handloom bunkars family didn't allow any outsider to interview female members of their family. In the focus group discussion, everybody views have been incorporated like young, middle age and old age handloom bunkar to analyse the ground reality of handloom bunkars. Didn't find government officials for the interview as they were not ready for the interview despite continuous request.

Secondary Data Regarding this, different sources of secondary data have been used for various purposes. Some of the sources that have been used in this study are as follows. National Handloom Development Corporation, Ministry of Textiles, Co-operatives, Micro Small and Medium Enterprises, Census of India, Banaras Bunkar Samiti, Trade Facilitation Centre, Census of India, Banaras Bunkar Samiti, Annual report of Textile Ministry, District industrial profile and Statistical abstract of Varanasi are considered as the rich and important sources. Besides the source discussed above, different literary works such as books, gazetteers, headlines from the eminent newspapers, journals (national and international), articles, websites, magazines and different other important information from the internet have been used to get the desired result of this research work.

Methodology is a path taken to solve research problems in a systematic manner (B.N. Ghosh, 1982). The design of this study research is based on both primary survey and secondary data. In order to analyse the handloom Bunkars

of Varanasi, qualitative and quantitative method have been used to get the desired outcome of the study area. Descriptive and analytical method have been used for comprehensive knowledge of handloom Bunkars living conditions. Varanasi district map has been digitized with all its handloom clusters by the help of Arc GIS 10.3 version. To improve the living conditions of handloom Bunkars remedial approach have been used.

Result and Discussion

Handloom weaving community of Varanasi is divided into three categories like Weavers/Bunkars, Girastas and Gaddidars. Bunkars are also called by the name of Weavers and they purchase raw materials (Fig. 6) for their Banarasi saree from Girastas, Gaddidars, open market and government handloom weaving service centre. Among them, maximum weavers buy raw material from the Girastas followed by Gaddidars then open market and very few bunkars went to government weaving service centre because it is closed most of the time (One of the respondents, 2016). When it is open then, there is no raw material because it provides raw material at a subsidised rate. There is also frequent cases of black marketing in it (Table 2). Bunkars lie at the bottom of the hierarchy of weaving community (Chand, 2016). Girastas are in the middle and under whom ten to twenty Weavers are working. Gaddidars remains at the top of the hierarchy and twenty Girastas are working under a Gaddidar. (Fig. 8). Since independence handloom products were never taxed but the recent step of Goods and Service Tax (GST) kept the handloom products under 5 per cent tax slap and raw materials used in it are under 12 per cent. Which result in the abrupt rise in the price of handloom products.

Today, Handloom bunkars of Varanasi mostly belong to Muslim community like Ansari, Halakhor, Khan etc. It is very surprising that during the holy month of Ramadan, Muslim bunkars perform their work of weaving for the longer time in a more effective and efficient manner than any other month in a year (Zuber,

2016). Despite whole day fasting, they prepare more sarees in the month of Ramadan than any other months. It is only because of the blessing (barquat) of Allah. In the month of Ramadan, they are only busy in their work of weaving and worship. They avoid to go outside their house unnecessarily, that they do in other months. They also have a very busy schedule of Namaz and Tarabi that they avoid in other months. But, in the holy month, they do it right from the early morning until midnight (Arif, 2016).

Way forward

Banarasi saree and its products like cushion cover, ladies purse, kurtis, curtains etc. have very good demand in the domestic market. But, there are very few bunkars who are ready to prepare them. The main reason is that they are not getting the legitimate wage for their weaving work that's why they are ready to do any other work like rickshaw pulling, fruit selling, vegetable selling etc. instead of their ancestral handloom weaving. There are series of incidence which contributes to the continuous decline in the handloom cottage

Fig: 8 Hierarchy of Weaving Community (Author, 2016)

Table 2: Sources of Raw Materials Procurement

Sources	Raw Materials (per cent)
Girastas	80
Gaddidars	7
Open Market	10
Government Institute	3

Source: Primary Survey (Author, 2016)

industry. In the 1980s, war in the middle-east countries like Iran-Iraq war to show their hegemony in the middle east followed by Iraq attack on Kuwait under the leadership of Saddam Hussein in 1990s to establish Iraq dominance on oil reserves of Kuwait. In 1997, Asian countries face a great financial depression followed by the attack of the USA on Iraq in 2003. Who act as global patrolling power and under this USA fulfils its hidden interest of establishing hegemony on the oil reserves of Iraq. There are three stakeholders in the middle-east Iran, Saudi Arabia and Israel. All three are the main importer of Banarasi sarees and its different products. After all the above crisis that have been discussed, they have totally stopped the import of handloom products from India in it Banarasi sarees and its products contribute the major share. After this, there is a sudden decline for the demand of handloom products and it continues till today. Because of it, there is a huge migration of handloom bunkars of Varanasi to other states like Tamil Nadu, Karnataka and Gujarat. From 1996 to 1997, Janta Dal Secular (JDS) party was ruling in the centre which was led by H.D. Deve Gowda. During that period, there was a burning demand from Karnataka to stop the import of Chinese silk because in India most of the silk market is controlled and owned by Marwaris of Karnataka. Considering it, JDS party put ban on import of Chinese silk to protect the domestic silk owners. This step of government create a huge shortage of silk supply in the market and bunkars didn't find any place to purchase silk. This shortage was totally pre-planned and master strategy of Karnataka Marwaris to become rich within the short span of time. It is very shocking to see that everybody know that there is only one community involved in it. Even the government didn't take any step against them because Marwari's were their main vote bank. After facing various problem bunkars tries to buy silk in black from the Marwari's. When they take that silk to their house then, they saw that there is a raid conducted by local police administration in their house. Several bunkars

were put behind the bars for purchasing the silk in black but none of the Marwari's were arrested. Within one year JDS party lost its majority in the Lok Sabha and Bharti Janta Party (BJP) under the leadership of Atal Bihari came to power in the centre. BJP instantly allow the import of Chinese silk but it was too late. There were so many cases of suicide in the bunkars family.

Conclusion

Geographical Indication status has been given to Banarasi sarees since 2009. But, it didn't bring any significant change in the upliftment of Varanasi handloom bunkars. With the coming of various new technologies like WhatsApp and Facebook, it can be easily breached. Interestingly, very few bunkars are aware of the fact that their products have been given Geographical Indication (GI) status since 2009. There is also misuse of GI status of Banarasi sarees like shopkeepers sell their sarees in the name of Banarasi to their consumers to gain more money from them. This habit of shopkeepers is also one of the major cause for the decline in the demand of Banarasi sarees. These shopkeepers also misrepresented their sarees as Banarasi in several government exhibitions as well. They also sell synthetic silk in the name of real one. MNREGA (Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Act) which came into force in 2005. Attract several bunker because in MGNREGA, they have to work only 8 hours and in return, they get good wages which is more than the handloom weaving work of 12 hours. MGNREGA is a central government scheme in which, they were given the secured job of 200 days in a year. On the other hand, handloom weaving is an informal cottage industry where there is no security of even tomorrow you will get your handloom labour wage or not. After considering all these many young bunkars have changed their ancestral work of weaving and many are also thinking to shift. In this regard majority of the bunkars, who are engaged in the profession of weaving are becoming old and after some years they will

retire from their ancestral weaving work. Who will be the next to carry on this rich cultural heritage of India? To address all these sorts of problems Ministry of Minority Affairs has launched the USTTAD (Upgrading the Skills and Training in Traditional Arts/Crafts for Development) scheme in Varanasi. To protect and preserve the rich handloom traditional heritage of Varanasi. To provide better employment opportunities in the handloom sector.

Suggestions

- There is a need to fully stop the black marketing of silk supply in the market.

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References

- Ansari, Mohd Shoaib. (2016), Assessing the Information Needs of Weavers of Banaras: A Conceptual Analysis, *International Science Community Association*, 4 (4), pp. 1-4.
- Bose, Tarun Kanti. (2015), *Globalization Pushes Varanasi Weavers to Hunger and Death*. Edited by Dr. Lenin Raghuvanshi. Varanasi, Uttar Pradesh Asian Human Rights Commission.
- Chaudhry, Jyoti Bhasin and Pant, Suman, (2016), A Study on Design Ornamentation of Banaras Brocades with Motifs Inspired from Nature. *International Association of Scientific Innovation and Research*, pp. 16-64.
- Eck, D.L. (1982), *Banaras City of Light*, N.J. *Princeton University Press* (Princeton, USA).
- Faisal, Sana. (2016), The Decline of Varanasi Silk Handloom Cottage Industry: A Case Study of Brocade Weaving Community in Varanasi. *Chitrolekha International Magazine on Art and Design*.
- Ghosh, B.N. (1982), New Delhi, Sterling Publishers Pvt. Ltd.
- Gutschow, Niels. (1994), *Varanasi/Benares The Centre of Hinduism?* *Erdkunde*, pp.194-209.
- Kaur, Jasminder. (2016), The Magnificent Weave of Banarasi Jamdani. *International Journal of Recent Research Aspects*, 3 (4), pp. 30-36.
- Ministry of Textiles. (2011), "Handloom." Annual Report, New Delhi, www.ministryoftextiles.gov.in, pp. 95-104.
- Savitri, P. Sujathamma and C. Ramanamma. (2013), Glory of Indian Traditional Silk Sarees. *International Journal of Textile and Fashion Technology*, 3 (2), pp. 61-68.
- Shaleni Bajpai, Anjali Karolia and Amita Pandya. (2015), Intervention of Newer Design for Handloom Brocade Sari of Varanasi. *International Journal of Research in Humanities and Social Studies*, 2 (11), pp. 37-42.

- Awareness programme like Hunar Haat should be conducted at a regular interval to aware the weavers about various Bunkars welfare schemes.
- Provisions under the Geographical Indications of Goods (Registration and Protection) must be strengthened.
- Linking handloom Bunkars to the online platforms like Amazon, Flipkart and Snapdeal may be helpful for them to sell their handloom products at a better price.
- Strong ministerial will also play an instrumental role in the revival of handloom cottage industry.

Sharma, Raj. (2016), *Market Research for Promotion of India Handloom Brand*, National Handloom Development Corporation, Governemnt of India, New Delhi, pp. 57-69.

Singh, Amrita Naik and Shailaja D. (2009), Exquisite Banarasi silk sarees. Vol. 47. No. 11. *Indian Silk*, pp. 19-21.

Tanaka, H. (1988), On the Geographic Study of Pilgrimage Places, In *Pilgrimage in World Religions*. Berlin.

The Gazette of India. (2009), Ministry of Law and Social Justice, New Delhi, Thursday, 30 December.